

The Beautiful Body and Healthism in HIV/AIDS Campaign Graphics

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Abstract

This paper will look at HIV/AIDS campaigns as a form of advertising 'selling' the ideology of health through the utilisation of different emotions. By analysing three contemporary Australian campaigns aimed at gay men, the paper examines the relationship between the concept of 'healthism', and the design strategies used to promote safer sex practices.

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The technique of advertising is to correlate feelings, moods or attributes to tangible objects, linking possible unattainable things with those that are attainable, and thus reassuring us that the former are within reach. (Williamson, 1983: 31)

Introduction

The AIDS virus is invisible to the naked eye, and people living with HIV often show no visible signs of illness, hence prevention campaigns can be seen in industrialised countries as the ‘face’ of the epidemic, through which a visual image is constructed, opinions formed and knowledge generated (Chan and Donovan, 2006). This is the sociocultural language of HIV/AIDS, or the ‘cultural construction’ of the epidemic. By this is meant the various ways in which HIV/AIDS is perceived by society, and the meanings that are assigned to images, language and metaphors (Treichler, 1988; 1999). The role of the designers creating campaigns therefore becomes crucial in shaping the sociocultural course of the epidemic. Understanding and analysing the messages presented by social marketing campaigns is essential to understanding the public perceptions of HIV/AIDS, and the behaviour and practices used by individuals and groups in an attempt to manage perceived risk.

The primary focus of most HIV/AIDS campaigns is the promotion of health through prevention or to counter the stigmatisation of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA). In order to achieve this the campaigns must affect viewers in such a way that they will change ‘risky’ sexual practices and ‘undesirable’ social behaviour, or maintain ‘safe’ practices. Just as advertising utilises a number of tactics to create emotional responses in the target audience, social marketing campaigns appeal to a number of different emotions to influence the viewer into making the ‘right’ choices. The campaigns aim at ‘selling’ health as a value by appealing to certain emotions such as lust (sexual desire), fear (self preservation), and responsibility (care for others or the community).

As health preservation is the main goal of these messages, this paper will argue that each design strategy should be seen in the context of ‘healthism’; a ‘health-valuing culture’ in which governments ‘include protecting the public’s health among their most important domestic duties’ (Crawford, 2006: 402) and in which individuals are held personally accountable for their health as proof of individual autonomy and good citizenship. In campaigns, as in advertising, the visual language of health is conveyed through the beauty ‘ideal’ of the physically fit body. Though the campaigns discussed in this paper use quite different design strategies, they all utilise the image of the ideal body or idealised social situations to promote the value of health.

Healthism and the Beautiful Body

During the 19th century with the industrial revolution in need of a healthy working population, and the emergence of medicine as a scientific practice, health became a social ideal and health promotion a priority of the state. On this foundation 'healthism' has manifested itself as one of the key values of capitalist society (Crawford, 1994). The second half of the 20th century saw health as an ideology grow into a 'super-value' (Crawford, 2006), along with the emergence of the 'risk society', in which a feeling of uncertainty, the fragmentation of culture, and breakdowns in traditional values, left individuals feeling vulnerable to an unlimited range of threats and hazards (Lupton, 1999). As Crawford (1984) describes, healthism has emerged out of the growing problem of human identity, as a way to define the healthy self in opposition to the unhealthy other. Being healthy is seen as synonymous with virtues of self-control, self-discipline, self-denial, and will power, while being ill is often associated with blame, weakness, and bad lifestyle choices.

Health promotion can be understood in the context of this culture. The role of social marketing campaigns is to promote self-control and self-regulation through the modification of behaviour. Therefore designers, when appealing to certain emotions of responsibility, self-discipline or blame, are playing into deep rooted beliefs of health as a strong social value and an identity defining virtue.

Health is visualised through the metaphor of the beautiful body. Particularly since the 19th century the demarkation of the healthy (beautiful) as visually distinct from the ill (ugly) has been essential in establishing boundaries between the two. As Gilman (1995: 52) writes: 'Illness, deformity, loss of function, ageing, mal-proportion, infection, risk – all the categories that in medical thought defined deviancy from the healthy norm become one with the notion of the ugly'. A beauty ideal of the healthy slim (female) or (muscular) male body has been created through advertising and popular culture as the object of social and sexual desire. Similarly, as Gilman (1995) points out, HIV/AIDS campaigns – though dealing with the prevention of illness – utilise the image of the healthy beautiful body in various ways to attract the attention of the viewer and to illustrate the invisibility of HIV. The decision to use healthy looking models in the design of campaigns is essential to the construction of the epidemic as 'invisible'.

Lust and Sexual Desire

Sexual desire is one of the most used selling points in conventional advertising. The erotic body as an 'object of desire' has been used to advertise almost any type of consumer goods (Reichert

and Lambiase, 2003). Though the consumer is well aware that it is not sex itself which is for sale, the product comes to 'mean' something to the consumer by reference to sex and eroticism. Thus, the product is symbolised through references to the human emotion of sexual desire (Williamson, 1983).

In the case of safer sex campaigns the 'advertisement' is both selling a 'product' (health) and simultaneously selling the safer sex experience as a product. In other words, the visual reference to fun, 'hot', or loving sex is linked to the 'advertised' safer sex practice. The campaigns focus on the eroticism of safer sex, and challenge the notion that 'good' sex is compromised by condom use. The goal is to persuade the target audience that they can have both. The models used in the campaigns fit the social norm of the ideal sexually attractive body, and therefore portrays safer sex as erotic, and someone engaging in safer sex as desirable. Within the culture of healthism an active 'healthy' sex life is seen as imperative to a full healthy lifestyle. By attempting to make safer sex normative, the campaigns convey the message that by ignoring the advice of the campaign, the viewer would not only risk their health or the health of their partner through possible HIV transmission, but also the health of their sex life. Though sustaining physical health is ultimately the aim of the campaign, this becomes a sub-message confined to the text, while a healthy sex life visualised through beautiful bodies is the graphic selling point. *Protection (2008)*

As gay men have continuously been the target of HIV/AIDS campaigns for the past twenty five years, designers of the campaigns must persistently find new ways of getting safer sex messages across. A recent campaign by the Melbourne-based Victorian AIDS Council/Gay Men's Health Centre (VAC/GMHC) pushes the boundaries of lust as a tool to promote condom use. As described in a radio interview with Mike Kennedy, the Executive Director of VAC/GMHC, the organisation decided they needed to try a different tactic after seeing an increase in new HIV notifications, predominantly amongst gay men in their 30s and 40s. These men knew how to protect themselves, but were still taking risks. The campaign aims at tackling mythologies about safer sex being boring and conforming to normative notions of 'the good gay citizen' (Kennedy and D'Macho, 2008).

In attempting to break down these myths, the campaign graphics – booklet, magazine advertisement, tea towel and website – use real pornographic images in combination with safer sex information and instructions. The design integrally links feelings of lust and sexual desire with 'healthy' sexual practices. The men portrayed conform to the body ideal of a desirable sex partner, while the sexual acts depicted illustrate the fantasy ideal of 'hot' 'raunchy' sex. Simultaneously, instructions on how to put on a condom or advice on safety are superimposed onto the fantasy. In a spread from the booklet, a white square with the words 'What is going on inside?' must be scratched off to reveal the model wearing a condom (Fig. 1). The booklet is

shrink-wrapped with a plain black cover stating: ‘Warning: sexually explicit material for gay men.’ These design ‘gimmicks’ create curiosity (the viewer is enticed to find out what is inside the book or underneath the square); and action (the viewer must physically rip open the wrapping and scratch off the square to get to both the porn and the safer sex message).

Figure 1: Spread from campaign booklet. *Protection* © Victorian AIDS Council/Gay Men’s Health Centre, 2008.

The design therefore functions on different levels. It creates an appeal by being exclusive (‘sexually explicit material for gay men’); it delivers useful instructions and information; while offering appealing erotic adult material, which can function as regular pornography.

According to VAC/GMHC this has been their most successful campaign to date, with a great deal of positive feedback from the target audience. Kennedy (2008) explains the general opinion of gay men as: ‘We don't want to hear it from the Health Department. We don't want to hear it from a doctor. We want to hear it from someone who knows what it is like, and who is doing it.’ This suggests that in a ‘healthist’ culture, where individuals are expected to take active steps to ensure their own safety, messages from institutions and authorities are not thought to be useful or welcome. Instead individual agency can be created through example. By seeing a visual display of how healthy sexual behaviour can still be attractive, exciting and ‘hot’, the target audience receives useful instructions on how to incorporate similar behaviour into their own risk management strategies.

Fear and Blame

Another approach to health promotion is through the use of ‘scare’ campaigns or ‘shock’ tactics. This strategy is often used in anti-smoking campaigns showing horrific effects of smoking on the

body. This type of campaign aims at coercing the public into making ‘healthy’ choices by showing the consequences of a deviation from the recommended normative lifestyle.

Fear-based campaigns were at times used in early Australian HIV/AIDS campaigns; most notably the 1988 *Grim Reaper* campaign produced by the Australian government. The campaign video showed a cloaked skeletal figure killing Australian men, women and children with a bowling ball. Since then HIV/AIDS related scare campaigns are rarely used in Australia. There are several reasons for this: firstly the campaigns were often seen as stigmatising people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA); secondly the introduction of anti-retroviral drugs (HIV medication) has meant that many people with HIV live relatively normal lives, and the death threat of AIDS is seen as less urgent; and thirdly, research has shown fear-based tactics tend to be ineffective, and even counter-effective by alienating the target audience (Batrouney, 2004). However, the recent rises in HIV infection in Australia has lead some organisations to believe more hard hitting tactics are needed to create awareness of the severity of HIV.

HIV. It's a Life Sentence (2007)

One such fear-based campaign is created by Queensland Positive People (QPP). Though the campaign strategy is not as overtly ‘fear based’ as the *Grim Reaper*, it does utilise feelings of fear, guilt and trepidation, as well as responsibility. In 2006 – in a response to a 50% rise in HIV notifications in Queensland – QPP conducted two focus tests to discuss effective prevention tactics with groups of HIV positive gay men. The resulting campaign – consisting of three posters, a web banner and condom packs – aims at conveying the message that there are consequences to HIV, and though infection is no longer a ‘DEATH sentence’, it is still a ‘LIFE sentence’ as there is no cure (Queensland Positive People, 2007a; 2007c; 2007b). The objectives are ‘to decrease risk behaviour and reduce further rises of HIV infections in Queensland [...] The campaign also contains elements which ask all people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) to be equally responsible for prevention of HIV transmission.’ (Queensland Positive People, 2007d).

The three posters (Fig. 2-4), depicting men of various ages naked from the waist up, convey a number of ambiguous messages. Similar in design, each poster uses a different visual metaphor to illustrate the central message of HIV having serious consequences to one’s life. However, the vague reference to HIV as ‘reaching far and wide’ (Fig 2), ‘revealing many life effects’ (Fig. 3) and ‘packing a real punch – to many parts of your life’ (Fig. 4) fails to inform the viewer what the precise effects are. By leaving this open to interpretation the ominous visual atmosphere creates a feeling that ‘bad’ sexual practices, denial, and lack of self-control could have consequences to any or all parts of one’s life. The design therefore feeds into existing fears of ever present uncertainty, risks and dangers typical of the postmodern era. As the men all look healthy, HIV

becomes more than a threat to one's physical health, but rather a threat to one's identity as a healthy individual leading a desirable lifestyle.

Figure 2: Poster. *HIV: It's a Life Sentence* © Queensland Positive People, 2007.

Figure 3: Poster. *HIV: It's a Life Sentence* © Queensland Positive People, 2007.

Figure 4: Poster. *HIV: It's a Life Sentence* © Queensland Positive People, 2007.

The campaign refers to the notion of individual responsibility for health. HIV positive men are responsible for keeping the infection from spreading from their own 'unhealthy' selves to a 'healthy' individual, while HIV negative men are responsible for staying 'healthy'. There is a strong appeal to moral responsibility, particularly in Figure 2, which asks men to 'dig up' their unclean conscience. The poster aims at invoking feelings of guilt and self-blame in HIV positive men who have possibly put partners of an unknown or negative HIV status at risk. Healthism in this context therefore extends from responsibility for oneself to responsibility for the health of others.

Compared to campaigns with positive safer sex messages, the design strategy does not refer to emotions of what is to be gained (a healthy/'hot' sex life), but to negative emotions of what is to be lost (a healthy moral and social identity). In a 'healthist' culture, in which health is a moral responsibility, the implication of becoming HIV infected is what Goffman (1963) calls a 'spoiled identity'. The 'life sentence' lies in the shift from an identity as a healthy individual to that of an ill/diseased/unhealthy individual. In legal terms a 'life sentence' is something given as a punishment for a horrific crime, only surpassed by a 'death sentence'; thus linking HIV with a life sentence automatically implies guilt and blame of HIV positive men, while attempting to provoke fear in HIV negative men.

Caring and Community

Another design approach to HIV/AIDS prevention is an appeal to feelings such as love, friendship, caring and community. As with the more explicit safer sex campaigns positive

emotions are used to 'sell' specific desirable social behaviours. The messages are focused on social identity instead of sexual lust, and play into ideologies of healthy emotional ties. The designers of these campaigns address the fact that HIV/AIDS spreads through interaction between people; a set of complex interactions in which decision making about safer sex practices involves much more than instructions on condom use. In order to make informed choices individuals need to feel that preventative actions are mutually and socially accepted; something which can only happen if the parties feel comfortable in the particular social setting. Therefore these campaigns shift the focus away from health as individual responsibility to health as a common responsibility, and aim at making preventative practices a natural part of social interaction.

Mates look after each other (2005)

Mates look after each other... it's what we do (Fig. 5-6) is a campaign created by the AIDS Council of New South Wales (ACON). It shows different scenarios in which gay and lesbian 'mates' and lovers take care of each other by making informed decisions about sexual health, drug practices and moral support.

The campaign graphics utilises emotions of longing for a strong, united, supportive gay and lesbian community, which references the unified community response to the Australian AIDS epidemic of the 1980s and early 90s. The Australian response is seen worldwide as remarkable in that the government worked closely with the most affected communities of injecting drug users, prostitutes and homosexuals, using harm reduction strategies instead of condemnations of the practices as deviant (see for example Sendziuk, 2003). The urgency of fighting the devastation of so many ill and dying people created a strong feeling of a united gay community; something which has changed after the introduction of antiretroviral drugs in what has been called the 'post-AIDS' era of an 'undetectable crisis' (Race, 2001) in which the responsibility of health has shifted from the community to the individual. In such an age prevention efforts must attempt to create 'sustainable' sexual cultures, where safer sex and drug practices are the social norm. The campaign works to counter the effects of healthism as an individual enterprise, and simultaneously reinforces healthism as a social norm.

Figure 5: Poster. *Soul Mates* © AIDS Council of New South Wales, 2005.

Figure 6: Poster. *Good Mates* © AIDS Council of New South Wales, 2005.

The visual language of the posters – as in the print advertising – shows ‘ideal’ scenarios of for example the loving relationship (Fig. 5), and the supportive circle of friends (Fig. 6). The health message is visually secondary in small print, while there is an emphasis on what soul/good mates ‘do’. Therefore to be a true part of this community and achieve access to these desirable social relationships the viewer must ‘do’ what the campaign suggests. The designer has hereby linked essential values of love, companionship, friendship and belonging to instructions on how to keep the community healthy. As in the *Protection* campaign, the designers appeal to the viewer by showing the fantasy of a desirable lifestyle obtainable by following the campaign guidelines. The

visual message works both through the idealised healthy and happy looking models, and the longing for an idealised healthy community and healthy social relationships.

Conclusion

Although HIV/AIDS prevention campaigns have the same overall goal – to sustain health – the design tactics used vary greatly, and appeal to a range of different emotions. The organisations producing the campaigns each have arguments for choosing a particular approach rooted in social research, focus testing, target audience, and the sociocultural course of the epidemic. Designs promoting positive messages use similar language to advertising in ‘selling’ prevention behaviour through ideologies of good sex, love, friendship or community; while designs utilising negative feelings of fear, trepidation and guilt attempt to alert the viewer to the consequences of risk behaviour.

All three campaigns discussed in this paper attempt to deal with the fact that after more than twenty-five years HIV/AIDS is still a serious issue within the Australian gay community, and ‘sustainable’ sexual cultures (Race, 2001) must be continuously promoted. Each campaign can be seen to build on some of the key concepts of a ‘healthist’ society, in which health has ‘become a crucial terrain upon which contemporary, personal identity is fashioned’ (Crawford, 1994: 1348); and in which the beautiful body is a metaphor for both physical and social health.

The *Protection* campaign appeals to the ideal of ‘hot’ sex as a priority for ‘healthy’ sexually active gay men. The campaign booklet not only alludes to feelings of lust, but in being a pornographic object in itself potentially creates lust; a lust which is linked to condom use. The campaign aims at finding the balance between capturing the interest of the men it aims to reach through seductive visuals, while getting the public health message across. The *HIV. It’s a life sentence* campaign, on the other hand, attempts to communicate an unpopular message through appealing to feelings of blame, and fears of an uncertain ‘unhealthy’ destiny. The healthy looking models placed within the sinister visual atmosphere shows the ambiguity of the healthy/unhealthy identity within the current epidemic. Though the message that HIV is still incurable and has real consequences to one’s life is clear, it is not immediately apparent who the campaign is speaking to, and what those consequences are. Finally, the *Mates* campaign attempts to query the notion of individual responsibility for health. Through the use of idealised social scenarios it utilises positive human interaction to unite the gay and lesbian community against the continued threat of HIV/AIDS, risky drug use and homophobia. Looking at the three campaigns it becomes apparent that the strategy choices made by the designers of the campaigns are vital in creating meaning and provoking emotions in an otherwise ‘invisible’ epidemic.

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